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Collaboration and Policy Making in
Adaptation Planning

The Impact of a Boundary Organization in Hungary

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Collaboration and Policy Making in Adaptation Planning: The Impact of a Boundary Organization in Hungary

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Abstract: To assess the possible impacts of climate change and plan the necessary adaptation measures, countries need to analyze complex and multilayered information. Data often belongs to different disciplines and institutions and is hard to interpret for policy making in its raw form. Boundary organizations have a pivotal role in facilitating discussion between academic and political actors and producing tools to assist in decision-making processes. Hungary, an Eastern European country, faces climate change effects ranging from changes in precipitation patterns to increasing frequency of weather extremities. This article examines the establishment of a boundary organization, the National Adaptation Centre, and its decision support tool, which aims to assist the territorial planning of the country. Through this, we identify the extent to which the National Adaptation Geo-Information System (NAGiS) tool has had an impact on collaboration pattern designs and policy making. The study finds that NAGiS supports policy development at different levels of governance. At the same time, the introduction of this information and communication technology tool was not sufficient to create a breakthrough or counteract other factors such as the low salience of the issue at the national level. Furthermore, the introduction of NAGiS did not change formal structures or procedures. However, it did have an impact on attitudes toward data sharing, which in turn shaped collaborative practices. The organizations involved generally evaluated the effects of the tool on their collaboration as positive and lasting beyond the development phase of the project. Changed attitudes may prove important for enhanced internal collaborative governance down the line.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance, Climate Change Adaptation, ICT Tools, Policy Design, Boundary Organizations

Introduction

Climate change is a cross-sectoral issue that needs collaboration between the different disciplines, political leaders, and decision-making levels (Leck and Simon 2013). Under the strong influence of an evidence-based scientific background, environmental and climate policy is often assisted by boundary organizations (Gustafsson and Lidskog 2018). These agencies have been established to build a bridge between scientific and political actors (Guston 2001). This article examines the establishment of the National Adaptation Centre (NAC) in Hungary and the development of NAC's information and analysis tool, the National Adaptation Geo-information System (NAGiS), to analyze whether such a tool is linked to changes in collaboration and policy-making patterns. This is of importance mainly because climate change adaptation is a cross-sectoral and multidisciplinary issue. Key research in the area often focuses on organizations in North America or in large countries in the northwestern parts of the European Union (EU) (Guston 2001; Hoppe and Wesselink 2014; Kirchhoff, Esselman, and Brown 2015; O'Mahony and Bechky 2008; Graham and Mitchell 2016), making the case of Hungary important in that it represents the many small/midsize countries in the Union's periphery and thereby adds further empirical knowledge. In light of all of these, this current article contributes to the discussion on boundary organizations (see, e.g., Kirchhoff, Esselman, and Brown 2015). The results of the study can also be used for improved design of spatial climate adaptation measures, following the EU Strategy for the Danube Region, which involves fourteen countries across Central and Eastern Europe.

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The article begins with an overview of how the research was conducted (section 2). It then provides an overview of the state-of-the-art knowledge on the relation between boundary organizations, policy design, and climate change adaptation (section 3). Section 4 argues that climate change policy is more dependent on collaborative practices than other sectors and sets the scene for the analysis of the development of NAC and NAGiS. Section 5 provides insight into the usage of the tool, whereas section 6 identifies its effects on policy development and decision-making. Section 7 identifies the effects on collaboration. A conclusion rounds off the discussion, highlighting the results and bringing the different parts together.

Research Design

This article investigates the establishment of the NAC and its information and analysis tool, the NAGiS. Hungary is a EU member country located in the Carpathian Basin, with a relatively small territory of 93,023 km² (Kocsis 2018) and a population of just under 10 million, ranking 13th out of 27 in terms of the population size of the EU. NAGiS is a national initiative, and the focus of this study is thus at a national level. This work applies a case study approach (Stake 2000) and follows the instructions of the H2020-supported TROPICO project's analytical framework (Carstens et al. 2019). The case is typical (Gerring 2007, 91) of small/midsize countries in Continental Central East, and it is therefore likely that findings are generalizable, although more comparative hypothesis-generating research is needed. Research was done between October 2018 and January 2019, with a follow-up inquiry in December 2020. Desk research activities covered the legal, procedural, and scientific aspects of the establishment of NAGiS. These were supplemented by semistructured interviews involving key actors of the establishment and development process. Interview recordings have been transcribed, and texts have been coded and analyzed. Through our research we assumed that the effects of the boundary organization can be described with the impact of its information and analysis tool.

The study covers the tool NAGiS from its inception to its implementation, that is, from around 2010 until the end of 2018. The case study relies primarily on qualitative research methods, supplemented by statistical information on, for instance, the usage of the tool. The research was sequenced as follows: The first stage involved desk research in collecting all publicly available documentation about the initiative. This included project documentation from the current website of NAGiS as well as the funder Regional Environmental Center (REC), previous research on the tool in the form of scholarly articles in Hungarian and English and examples of strategy and decision documents based on or with reference to the NAGiS. In total, forty-three documents were reviewed to record all instances, which directly referred to the key aims of the study (impact on policy making and collaboration). Reviewed documents include the relevant national legislation (acts and government decrees on climate change), strategic and policy documents (National Strategy on Climate Change, National Framework Strategy for Sustainable Development), European Union, governmental and third sector reports, and relevant scholarly articles on the topic. Some of the documents are directly cited in the article, whereas others, used only for the analysis, are indicated in the Appendix.

In the second stage, a stakeholder map was produced, outlining the actors that were deemed key to the development of the tool, on the basis of the results of the first phase. Interview requests were first sent to the unit in charge of the operation of the tool, Mining and Geological Survey of Hungary (MBFSz), and interviews were then carried out in accordance with how closely the interviewees had been involved in the making and use of the tool.

The interviews took place between November 2018 and January 2019. A total of twelve persons were interviewed (see list in the Annex to this article). The interviews took place in person, at the interviewee's premises, except for three, which were conducted over the phone or internet-based voice services. Most interviews were conducted by two researchers to enhance the analytical purchase and validation of interpretations. Interviews were transcribed in the

original language (mostly Hungarian) and summarized in English. Informed consent was collected in writing from all respondents. Most interviewees agreed to be cited by name, but, for the sake of consistency, code words are used for all quotations and sources throughout this article. Research data collection complied with current Hungarian and European legislation.

Boundary Organizations and Climate Policy Design

Over the past few decades, changes observed in climate conditions and in the political processes associated with climate change have triggered a political demand for territorial responses to develop adaptation strategies. In the European Union, this takes place at the European community, national, and local levels. The development of these strategies calls for evidence-based approaches, especially in the field of integrated vulnerability assessments. Although territorial or spatial planning, in general, includes responsibility for reducing regional vulnerabilities and disparities, integrating adaptation goals into spatial strategies has proven to be complicated. A fundamental problem is the fragmented state of knowledge. Research is often carried out separately for different policy sectors, and researchers from different scientific disciplines set up projects independently of each other. This often makes it difficult to compare the research results among the different disciplines in view of methodological differences (Schmidt-Thomé and Greiving 2013). Therefore, multidisciplinary cross-sectoral collaboration and a common approach or methodology are called for.

Such collaboration is especially important for the spatial planning of the national adaptation strategies that European Union members are elaborating, following the White Paper “Adapting to Climate Change: Toward a European Framework for Action” (European Commission 2009), which explicitly stated that spatial planning should have a long-term strategic approach and the EU climate change adaptation strategy (European Commission 2013). However, member states have understood this in different ways, and, although Hungary’s National Climate Change Strategy (NCCS) acknowledges the relevance of spatial planning, the spatial context is not translated into practice (Greiving and Fleischhauer 2012). That strategy went through a process of revision since 2012 and was accepted by the National Assembly in late 2018. In 2016 and 2017, Hungarian regions (counties) were also required to develop their climate change strategies. This was the first time that climate change adaptation was considered for territorial planning at the subnational level, and currently there are plans to require municipalities to do the same.

Hungary, a Central European country located in the Carpathian basin, faces serious adaptation challenges: Rising temperature and more frequent heat extremities and changing precipitation patterns can be expected (Lakatos et al. 2012; Pieczka et al. 2018), leading to a dramatic decrease in surface water availability (Ellison 2010). As known hazards do not necessarily lead to vulnerability, it is rooted in societal and political issues (Cardona et al. 2012; Cutter 1996; Oliver-Smith et al. 2016). The current growth in the trend in housing poverty (Ámon et al. 2019), long-lasting segregation and marginalization (Rado 2020), and a solid structure of multilayered deprivation in the countryside (Koós 2015; Ripp 2018), which can trigger a host of climate-vulnerable chronic diseases (Juhász et al. 2010; Páldy et al. 2005), representing complex climate change adaptation challenges.

In this demanding situation, policies need to be based on solid grounds and developed with the use of the results of reliable research activities. Many European countries established boundary organizations to transfer and mainstream scientific results in policy development (Hoppe and Wesselink 2014). These organizations are located on the boundaries between politics and science. Although they provide the opportunity and incentives for collaboration, they involve both sides and have distinct lines of accountability to each (Guston 2001). Such institutions are necessary and effective in cases like climate change adaptation, where complex, multilayered challenges are to be addressed (Kirchhoff, Esselman, and Brown 2015). These establishments not only provide a platform for academic-political interaction but can also facilitate wider networks of much-needed stakeholders (O’Mahony and Bechky 2008) and mitigate spatial inequalities in access to information (Graham and Mitchell 2016).

Climate change adaptation is a complex task, because it involves multisectoral and multilayered challenges, including aspects that are hard to quantify. In preparation for decision-making, problems should be broken down into small, manageable parts that can be analyzed and reintegrated later. There is a growing body of tools assisting spatial decisions with geographical visualization, both for national- and community-level approaches (Lieske 2015). Hungary lacked a complex and multisectoral geographically processed data source related to climate change before NAGiS was initiated. As a European Union member, Hungary is obliged to adopt the EU's Adaptation Strategy, and as a signatory of the Kyoto Agreement, it is also committed to complying with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change measures.

Establishing National Adaptation Centre and the NAGiS Analysis Tool

In the early 2000s, a large project of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences investigated the possible impacts and adaptation measures with traditional research tools and methods. The "Change-Impact-Response" Project can be seen as the precursor to NAGiS, because it laid down the theoretical basis and shed light on many sectoral adaptation challenges (Kajner et al. 2017). During the project, carried out between 2003 and 2006, researchers from several academic and scientific institutions investigated the possible impacts of climate change and explored various options to respond to them. These researchers came from various fields, and it became clear that the territorial aspect could be the missing link between the different disciplines. In parallel, the government agency that dealt with territorial development at the time (VÁTI) began to integrate different data sources, and the first territorial climate vulnerability assessment methodology was developed.

Hungary is a signatory to the relevant international agreements and appears to be devoted to following a sustainable climate and energy pathway highlighted in different policy documents (Patkós et al. 2019). Building on the aforementioned multidisciplinary project results, the National Assembly accepted the first National Climate Change Strategy (NCCS-I) in 2008 (European Commission 2018; Westerhoff et al. 2010). Owing to changes in government structures after the elections in April 2010, climate policy became the Ministry for National Development's responsibility. The Ministry appointed a state secretary for energy and climate policy, who was open to new initiatives and was dedicated to supporting CCA activities. Later, he became the deputy director of the Geological Institution. Climate change-related legislation changed in 2012 with a bill that authorized the government to set up and maintain a geo-information system to assist the development of the national climate change strategy.

In the meantime, a new boundary organization, the NAC, had been set up under the supervision of the National Geological and Geophysical Institution, a body affiliated with the Ministry of National Development. NAC's primary role was to assist the government with information related to climate change policies. One of the Centre's first tasks was to initiate a feasibility study and start the preliminary negotiations for NAGiS with partners and possible donors. Eventually, the NAC took the lead on the initiative of NAGiS and approached the REC for Central and Eastern Europe, an international intergovernmental organization, which was coordinating funds from Norway/EEA Grants in Hungary.

In 2013, after successful negotiations, this project became the main element of the EEA Grants Adaptation to Climate Change program area in Hungary,² and REC became the grant operator, whereas the donor partner was the Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection and Emergency

² Norway contributes financially to the spatial development of the European Union with funds defined in the EEA Agreement. The EFTA countries Iceland, Lichtenstein, and Norway are the donors to the fund. EEA/Norway Grants support social and economic cohesion initiatives in different priority areas, with an important percentage (36.1% of the total) for grants on energy and climate programs (Jevnaker, Lunde, and Skjærseth 2015). The aim of the EEA Grants is to reduce economic and social disparities in the European Economic Area and strengthen bilateral relations between the donor and beneficiary states. Although the overall budget of the EEA/Norway is limited, it has a significant effect in the relations between Norway, EU, and beneficiary states. Grants create partnerships, and as Norway defines priorities and shapes the direction of the Grants, it can affect the developments in the beneficiary states (Johnsen and Rieker 2015).

Planning. The main reason for involving an external donor was that the area was underfunded and underprioritized by the mainstream parties, and the situation worsened after the change of government in 2010. According to an evaluation report prepared by the community of the Hungarian NGOs dealing with environmental issues, governmental performance on the environmental policy was weak between 2010 to 2012 (Csalán NGO 2012). According to a former high-level governmental official, the environmental initiatives were successful only when high-level officials personally supported them, given that there was generally little political support within the government (interviewee WP4-012). Setting up an ICT tool like NAGiS required strong ownership from those who advocated it. Governmental budget for climate policy was limited, necessitating external funding, and this is where the EEA/Norway funds become relevant. Interviewees generally appreciated the cooperation between these actors because it worked well despite taking place during a period of tension between the Government of Hungary and the Norwegian grants management.

The government published a decree in early 2014 setting out the frame for the development of NAGiS, giving competences to the actors and regulating the possible user groups. Access rights are also regulated by this decree, including the registration procedure for the twenty-four possible organizational groups with bodies that are unlikely to use the tool, such as the Constitutional Court. Furthermore, important categories of users appear to be excluded (e.g., private sector and NGOs). However, external parties in a contractual relationship with these bodies can also request ad hoc access, as can those who are represented in, for instance, advisory or consultative boards. According to an interview with a former leader of NAC who was involved in the development (WP4-004), the main reason for giving these specific user groups access was to limit the number of users so as to prevent overload of servers and facilitate control over user access.

The NAC led the development of NAGiS with a consortium of various key stakeholders. Later, various side projects were introduced and financed separately, concerning the addition of new functions and layers to the system—this incentivized data sharing between the different actors. Such shared data could consist of, for instance, information on physical environment, natural habitats, demography, and social and economic issues. Data in NAGiS covers a wide spectrum, showing that the adaptation analyses are cross-disciplinary and incorporate different thematic fields of both natural and social sciences.

NAGiS was introduced to the public and users on May 1, 2016. A second NAGiS project (NAGiS 2) was started in late 2016, financed by the National Environmental and Energy Efficiency Operative Programme of the European Regional Development Funds. The main objective of NAGiS 2 was to introduce tools assisting local governments in the decision-making process related to local climate policy development and to continue developing existing databases, methodologies, and assessment modules. It was also aimed at making the system more user-friendly. In 2018, new NAGiS services were introduced. Other additional developments were introduced in 2019, including the Leadership Information System and support functions for local governments, as more user-friendly surfaces to access matured information (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Development Timeline of NAC and NAGiS
 Source: Molnár and Svensson

Features of the NAGiS Tool

The overall objective of the National Adaptation Geo-information Service (NAGiS; in Hungarian, NATÉR) is to establish a geo-information and data system to assist climate change impact and vulnerability assessments. Using a geospatial approach, it assists in the preparation of strategies and spatial planning (Sütő 2016). It was developed to be a multipurpose geo-information system that could facilitate policy-making, strategy-building, and decision-making processes related to the impact assessment of climate change and the country's necessary adaptive measures. Relevant and accurate data is essential for planning, and, ideally, a geographical information system should provide the necessary quantitative and qualitative information (Kajner et al. 2017).

The main purpose of the innovation was to develop a GIS system that assists climate change adaptation in Hungary. Geographic information systems (GIS) are functional software applications that provide information generated from geographically pinpointed data. A GIS solution can integrate useful features to assist decision-making processes related to climate change, including layering, querying, geo-referencing and, most importantly, visualization. A GIS solution lets professionals assess a variety of geographically pinpointed data by visualizing them on maps, putting layers on each other to identify, for example, linkages and commonalities. Although challenges related to data availability and data error and understanding of climate modeling results' uncertainty are inevitable, GIS applications can generate easily understandable outputs that may support climate policy-related decision-making activities (Woodruff, Vitro, and BenDor 2018).

Although it is not the purpose of this article to provide a traditional evaluation of the value of the tool, understanding its key features is relevant to the effects and consequences it had on decision-making and participating organizations. According to the operating rules, the applications and services fall into two groups: openly accessible features and features accessible after authorization.

Openly accessible features and content include articles, scientific papers and short reports in HTML and PDF formats, e-services (browser-based map application), a browser-based NAGiS Metadata explorer, Web Map Service for Desktop GIS environments, and interactive inquiry and visualization. Direct access to the NAGiS database is available on registration and decided on the basis of affiliation with one of the specified user groups.

The main feature of the NAGiS portal is the web-based map visualizer, which can be accessed without registration and login. The visualizer's base map is provided by an open-source solution, the OpenStreetMap base layer. In NAGiS map application, users can add different layers to visualize the various effects of climate change.

The data of NAGiS can also be accessed in desktop applications using Web Map Service compatible with the most used GIS applications. This allows professional users to carry out their analyses in their own surfaces, combining NAGiS information with their layers and base maps (e.g., municipal development maps). Using this information, a municipality or a stakeholder involved in territorial development can assess the different effects of climate change related to their locality. The system can be used to identify the most critical challenges and vulnerabilities and visualize them in a way that is easy to understand. For example, it visualizes excess mortality attributable to heatwaves as well. With related poverty indicators, one could approximate how deprivation, climate change, and demographic trends will shape health-related challenges in 2050 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Screenshot of the NAGiS Main Site

Source: NATÉR 2019

Effects on Policy Making and Decision-Making

NAGiS serves as a solution to provide spatially relevant transdisciplinary evidence primarily for climate policy development, but it also has the potential to serve other policy areas. It is important to note that NAGiS is not merely a GIS tool but that it goes beyond information provision by virtue of its capacity to carry out assessments (i.e., it has analytical capacity) and provides results as input for the development of different policy documents, especially climate change strategies. As climate change adaptation is a horizontal issue across sectors, NAGiS potentially provides input for developing other policy areas, especially territorial development, energy, and social policies. Our study identified NAGiS' capacity to influence the development of national-, county-level, and local strategic planning related to climate change.

NAGiS results were included at the national level in the revision of the NCCS-II. At the regional level, reports derived from NAGiS constituted the primary input for baseline chapters and sections related to expected effects in climate change strategies developed over the past years. The development of local-level climate change strategies of larger towns was also assisted by NAGiS, whereas some settlements assessed their climate vulnerability on their own using NAGiS means. Here, we elaborate on the territorial climate change strategies at the subnational level.

Because the national climate policy should be based on local conditions, the Government of Hungary dedicated European Regional Development Fund allocations to the county level and municipal climate strategies within the Environment and Energy Efficiency Operative Programme. Because they have responsibilities for territorial development planning in their respective areas, county governments were first out.

All twenty county governments and the capital city started developing their respective climate change strategies in 2016 and 2017. The development of county strategies was a long and complex process, supported with a how-to-guide and some reports constructed from NAGiS data. County governments built up consortiums from local stakeholders and specialized consultancy agencies or companies. The NAC worked on drafting some of the strategies as a subcontractor

and, in addition, private consultancy companies were involved in multiple strategy developments (interviews WP4-001, 002, 003, 010). County governments had to utilize their cross-sectoral stakeholder relations to develop the strategies. The documents had a predefined scope and structure, but county governments were free to prioritize their strategic goals and means. In other words, NAGiS provided a framework in which the policy was formulated, giving users freedom within some constraints. Several strategy documents are available on the websites of the respective county governments or project websites.

The “Methodological guide for the development of county climate strategies” was written by officials at the NAC in the year 2017. The guide suggests inviting the most critical stakeholders to collaborate and form a so-called “County Climate Platform.” This forum aims to provide a conciliation surface for strategy development. Yet it could also function as a “climate change working group” (a body defined in the guide for climate strategies) during the implementation period of the respective strategies (Bíró et al. 2017). Climate platforms were supported with an extensive report about the climate risks and expected effects in their relevant region, compiled by the NAC on the basis of the data available with NAGiS (Bíró et al. 2017). This report assisted strategy planners with relevant information to compile the vulnerability assessment sections. The methodological guide’s adaptation chapters focused on NAGiS data, and the reports provided by NAC were a compilation of the relevant maps of NAGiS (interviews WP4-001, 002, 003). This centralized approach ensured quality but also revealed a certain level of distrust toward the capacity at the local level, as indicated in the following quote:

Each county received their vulnerability information in this report because we were afraid that if the counties would use NAGiS they will get lost and not be able to distil anything from it. (Interview WP4-004)

Since NAC provided counties with the vulnerability profile reports, there was no need for other users to directly access NAGiS to comply with the strategy’s requirements. However, in some cases, climate platforms and consultants used the system on their own. An interviewed consultant (WP4-010) used NAGiS for eight to ten thematic adaptation areas to gain additional information needed for his analyses. He used the map tool and stuck to the visual analysis because it has the most effortless output to understand by decision makers. He triangulated the results with local experts’ professional opinion, who confirmed the relevance of the NAGiS-based findings. For more detailed data, the interviewee turned to other statistical sources and supplemented them with NAGiS information. Another interviewee, WP4-004, was involved in the quality assurance of the strategies. According to him, half of the counties visibly used NAGiS during the process. The key to success was to focus on vulnerability instead of spending dozens of pages on climatology and meteorology.

The Association of Climate-Friendly Municipalities, an NGO made up of local governments prioritizing climate issues, evaluated each strategy. The association has a secretariat with climate policy professionals that advised county governments through the process. Therefore, content-related control and supervision were provided to the counties in addition to the how-to guide.

Central level actors have also used NAGiS in decision-making, especially the General Directorate of Water Management and its water catchment directorates, an agency belonging to the Ministry of Interior. The agency has extensively used NAGiS for internal reports and presentations (WP4-009) and has the highest number of registered users. Decision makers welcomed the maps that showed climate change effects and served as supplements of these documents and presentations. NAGiS was also used in material related to a LIFE cofinanced project directed by the Ministry of Interior (MoI).

For further use, interviewees saw significant possibilities for inclusion in development plans and environmental impact assessments. It could even be a requirement for funding if integrated into the grant proposal evaluation structure of SECAP (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans) or the Territorial Development Operative Programme calls (interviews WP4-004, 010).

According to EU rules, environmental impact assessments are mandatory for many development projects but are sometimes perceived in Hungary as perfunctory and as a “box-ticking exercise.” Increasing the use of NAGiS in the assessment of climate-related risks would have the potential to change that (WP4-004).

Thus, NAGiS has been used in various materials available to policy makers at different levels to make decisions in the field of climate change adaptation, but this does not mean the strategies have indeed been implemented. As is well known from implementation research, strategy implementation requires political commitment, technical capacity, and resources (Uittenbroek et al. 2014). Given the relatively low salience of environmental issues, in general, and climate change adaptation in Hungary, there may be deficits in all these areas. In fact, as illustrated by the fraught procedure of arriving at a national climate change strategy, the introduction of an ICT tool was not enough to create a breakthrough or counteract other tendencies (the low salience of the issue at the national level). The introduction of NAGiS did not change formal structures or procedures, except opening data-sharing practices and changing collaborative practices. Thus, we see that the tool informed decision makers and decision-making in terms of availability of solutions, but this does not equal the increased quality of the entire policy process.

A tool such as NAGiS is a resource for policy makers and stakeholders that should save time and effort and improve the quality of decisions. However, at the municipal level it was often seen as something requiring more human and technological resources, that is, as being expensive. Therefore, the tool increased the efforts to conduct decision-making.

Effects on Collaboration

The effects of NAGiS on participating organizations vary. However, according to multiple interviewees, the work on the NAGiS tool contributed to a more cohesive and collaborative environment within the institution in charge of the development (NAC).

The effect of this project was that it brought together all the units of the institution. It developed such an integrated work method through the very special features of the tool, that it improved the entire organization’s coherence. We really could feel that. (Interview WP4-003)

Through this we could see how different parts come together, which led to the development of further research projects. (Interview WP-002)

Beyond the vital effect on the newly established NAC’s internal cohesion, it also strengthened the collaboration between the different government agencies that were involved.

It’s important that the collaborative culture between institutions clearly was improved through NAGiS...Slowly but surely the units got used to that they have a joint project. (Interview WP4-004)

Cooperation between academic disciplines has been strengthened (WP4-006), as an important positive effect on climate change research in the country.

The most critical obstacle to cooperation was the unwillingness to share data. The prevailing attitude seems to be that data is a valuable resource that each organization seeks to keep to itself because it can often be turned into monetary value in various ways. This may range from the direct sale of data to supplement the organization’s budget to show-casing the in-house data as proof of the organization’s value in budget negotiations with the state, as indicated by the following excerpt from an interview.

In Hungary, the budget of many institutes is not covered by the state. This proportion is usually around 30 percent or even lower. The other part of the budget has to be from other sources, such as selling datasets or national and international projects. So, it is a

sensitive issue if we make a publicly open database, that can be used basically by anybody, we cannot know where will land the data afterwards... We had side-projects around NAGiS, and this could be seen as a way to compensate these losses from not selling the data. We were able to make new, denser datasets and worked on new simulations, and these are not yet part of the NAGiS. (Interview WP4-006)

In the development of NAGiS, this reluctance to share data led to many lengthy talks and negotiations between the participating organizations. For instance, NAC could not secure data from the Department of Geodesy, Remote Sensing and Land Offices, under the Government Office of the capital city, Budapest. The reason specified for sharing the data was a regulation that involved actors but did not allow data transfer. The most essential talks were with the Meteorological Institute. These talks and many others (including Public Health Authority and the Ministry of Agriculture) were concluded successfully. However, regular data updates were never discussed, and this led to the risk of the system soon becoming obsolete.

The Norwegian Fund made clear that costs for data could not be claimed...it's an important lesson that international funders should not finance data sharing between state institutions, which does not make sense anyhow. (Interview WP4-004)

One way to get around this issue would be to rely more on user-generated content, but this did not work out owing to concerns about managing what users contribute and add (WP4-004).

The case study research strengthens the assessment that the intensity of collaboration in Hungarian public administration is generally low, even though the collaboration geared externally has improved, for example, through one-stop shops for public services. The interviewees all confirmed that it is hard to reach out to representatives from other organizations but that the NAGiS project was very positive in terms of improving collaboration.

Conclusion

Whether municipal or local, regional, or national in scope, the need for evidence-based information on climate change effects is common. The investigated system has potential in the development of different policies and impact assessments. We demonstrated that NAGiS has to provide sufficient information for all of these possible processes, which in itself is a challenge. Furthermore, we showed how collaboration between actors improved because of the tool. There is potential for local and regional actors to master their access and usage of data. This may foster more democratic and participative practices inside the bureaucracy, which can be seen in developing the county-level and municipal climate change strategies. The NAC provides tools to utilize scientific results through NAGiS and know-how through guidance documents for various user groups on a different level, fulfilling its role as a boundary organization. Developing an ICT tool providing information on the effects of climate change is only one step along the road. As shown in this case study, better collaboration between different disciplines and a wide range of governmental institutions is needed in data sharing and analysis. At the same time, on the receiving end, a user-friendly interface and easily actionable guidelines are necessary to utilize the outputs in policy development.

The development of such a tool may foster more democratic and participative practices inside the bureaucracy, which is likely to have some effects, albeit marginal, on democracy overall. This is especially the case at the local level, where political leadership, public administration, and citizenry are more closely intertwined than at the national level. This is especially important in countries that face challenges to democracy, such as in Hungary, which has frequently been criticized by international and European actors for democratic deficits (Csaky 2020; European Commission 2020). How ICT is used and how it will be put to use in the coming years in such countries is therefore of vital importance in Hungary and in the Central Eastern European region. The development of NAGiS shows an example of the collaboration in climate adaptation for countries on the periphery of the European Union and for states where climate policy issues are less salient.

Thus, the findings showcase the potential added value of promoting such tools beyond the immediate impact on climate adaptation. This suggests the relevance of further research on the interlinkage between climate adaptation and global values concerning cooperation and democracy, which should be of interest to scholars and stakeholders alike.

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Appendix

The following documents were used for the analysis but were not directly referenced in the text and hence not part of the reference list.

Brief on the National Adaptation Geo-Information System	https://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/en/node/161
Draft of the Second National Climate Change Strategy (2017–2030)	http://www.parlament.hu/irom40/15783/15783.pdf
Act nr LX. 2007 on UNFCC	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0700060.TV
Act nr. CCXVII. 2012 on the Implementation of EU ETS	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200217.TV
Government Decree nr 94/2014 (III.21.) on NAGiS	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1400094.KOR
Report on the Maintenance of NAGiS in 2014	https://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/besz%C3%A1mol%C3%B3_NATeR%20%C3%BCzemeltet%C3%A9s_150212_end.pdf
Report on the Maintenance of NAGiS in 2015	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/NAT%C3%A9R%20-%202015_%20%C3%A9vi%20%C3%89ves%20besz%C3%A1mol%C3%B3.pdf
Report on the Maintenance of NAGiS in 2016	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/NAT%C3%A9R%202016_%20%C3%A9vi%20%C3%BCzemeltet%C3%A9si%20Besz%C3%A1mol%C3%B3.pdf
Report on the Maintenance of NAGiS in 2017	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/Beszamolo_2017_alairt.pdf
Survey of Climate Awareness of Hungarian Local Governments	http://nakfo.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/default/files/files/NATER_onkormanyzati_tanulmany.pdf
Summary Report on NAGiS	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/Oszegzo_HU.pdf
SEERISK. 2014. Guideline on Climate Change Adaptation and Risk Assessment in the Danube Macro-Region, NDGDM	https://environmentalrisks.danube-region.eu/?mdocs-file=2012
NAGiS, as the Tool of the National Climate Policy. Presentation of Mr. Ferenc Hizó, Deputy Secretary of State at NAGiS Opening Conference, October 14, 2013	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/default/files/files/HF_NATeR_oktober14.pdf
Orosz, L. 2016. NATÉR Felhasználói Kézikönyv [NAGiS Users Guide]	http://mek.oszk.hu/18000/18042/18042.pdf
Pálvölgyi, T., and P. Selmecezi, eds. 2016. Tudásmegosztás, alkalmazkodás, éghajlatváltozás [Research and Development Report of NAGiS]	http://real.mtak.hu/41196/1/NATeR_kotet_MFGI_2016_BedeFA.pdf
NAGiS Terms and Conditions	http://nater.mbfisz.gov.hu/sites/nater.mfgi.hu/files/files/NATeR_USz_2018_09.pdf
National Framework Strategy for Sustainable Development	https://www.nfft.hu/nffs
Summary Report on the Governmental Implementation in 2015–16 of National Framework Strategy for Sustainable Development	http://www.nfft.hu/documents/1238941/1261771/NFFS_2_EHJ_1_mell%C3%A9klet_korm_int.pdf/36ea2a0f-9815-540e-77b8-61f95b7027fd

Informants Interviewed

<i>Code</i>	<i>Background</i>
<i>WP4-001</i>	Acting head of National Adaptation Centre
<i>WP4-002</i>	Acting deputy head of National Adaptation Centre
<i>WP4-003</i>	Awareness raising expert of National Adaptation Centre
<i>WP4-004</i>	Former head of National Adaptation Centre, climate policy expert
<i>WP4-005</i>	Independent expert on international development and humanitarian policy
<i>WP4-006</i>	Expert of Hungarian Meteorological Service on climate modelling
<i>WP4-007</i>	Expert of Regional Environmental Centre (programme coordinator for EEA Grants)
<i>WP4-008</i>	GIS expert at Disaster Management
<i>WP4-009</i>	Senior public servant at Water Management
<i>WP4-010</i>	Independent expert on climate policy
<i>WP4-011</i>	GIS expert at Norwegian Civil Protection
<i>WP4-012</i>	Former high-level government representative, policy expert

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The International Journal of Climate Change: Impacts and Responses seeks to create an interdisciplinary forum for discussion of evidence of climate change, its causes, its ecosystemic impacts, and its human impacts. The journal also explores technological, policy, strategic, and social responses to climate change.

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